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STUDII – ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯ – RESEARCHES

Valery Manko, Guram Chkhatarashvili

Kvirike: The Early Holocene Site in Western Georgia

Key words: Early Holocene, Kobuletian Culture, backed bladelets and microblades, pressing flaking, hunting weapons.

Cuvinte cheie: Holocenul timpuriu, cultura Kobuletiană, lame și microlame cu spate, tehnica prin presare, arme de vânătoare.

Ключевые слова: ранний голоцен, кобулетская культура, пластинки и микропластины с притупленными краями, отжимная техника, охотничье вооружение.

Valery Manko, Guram Chkhatarashvili

Kvirike: The Early Holocene Site in Western Georgia

The article is devoted to the publication of the Early Holocene Kvirike Site in Western Georgia. The site was the ancient hunting camp left by the carriers of Kobuletian Culture (X-VII millennium BC). The authors analyze the typology of artifacts from Kvirike complex, showing that its typology corresponds to the Kukrekian Culture and Donetsk Culture on the territory of Mountainous Crimea, Steppe Ukraine, and Moldova, and M'lefaat Culture on the territory of Iran and Iraq. The similarities of these cultures are best shown in the hunting weapons complexes. The similarities are not only in typology but in the technology of hunting tools production and in methods of their usage were observed. Accordingly, the authors conclude the existence of a zone of material cultures continuity on the territory of the Middle East, Western Georgia, Mountainous Crimea, and Steppe Ukraine. This continuity played an important role in further processes of the Neolithisation of East Europe.

Valery Manko, Guram Chkhatarashvili

Kvirike: Situl atribuit Holocenului timpuriu din vestul Georgiei

Articolul cuprinde rezultatele studierii/cercetării sitului Kvirike, atribuit Holocenului timpuriu din vestul Georgiei. Stațiunea reprezintă o tabără preistorică de vânătoare, utilizată de purtătorii culturii Kobuletiene (mileniul X-VII a.Chr.). Autorii analizează tipologia artefactelor din complexul de la Kvirike, arătând că tipologia vestigiilor corespunde celei atribuite culturii Kukrekian și culturii Donețk din arealul Crimei muntoase, din zona de stepă a Ucrainei și Moldovei, dar și culturii M'lefaat de pe teritoriile Iranului și Irakului. Similitudinile acestor culturi sunt cel mai bine evidențiate în complexele cu arme de vânătoare. Astfel, autorii ajung la concluzia că în arealul care cuprinde Orientul Mijlociu, vestul Georgiei, Crimeea muntoasă și stepa Ucrainei există o continuitate a culturii materiale, iar această continuitate a jucat un rol important în procesele ulterioare de neolitizare a estului Europei.

Валери Манько, Гурам Чхатарашвили

Kvirike: раннеголоценовая стоянка в Западной Грузии

Статья посвящена публикации материалов раннеголоценовой стоянки Квирикe в Западной Грузии. Стоянка представляет собой древний охотничий лагерь, оставленный носителями кобулетской культуры (X-VII тыс. до н. э.). Авторы анализируют типологию артефактов комплекса Квирикe, показывают, что та же типология повторяется в комплексах кукрекской и донецкой культур в Горном Крыму, степной полосе Украины и Молдавии, а также в комплексах млефаатской культуры на территории Ирана и Ирака. Подобность перечисленных культур лучше всего демонстрируют комплексы оснащения охотничьего вооружения. Сходство культур прослеживается не только в типологии, но и в технологии изготовления, и в методах применения охотничьего вооружения. Основываясь на таком сходстве, авторы констатируют наличие зоны непрерывности традиций материальной культуры на территории Среднего Востока, Западной Грузии, Горного Крыма и степной полосы Украины. Эта зона непрерывности сыграла важную роль в дальнейшем процессе неолитизации Восточной Европы.

Introduction

Kvirike is a small complex, left by carriers of Kobuletian Culture in the Early Holocene. At present time, much more informative complexes

of Kobuletian Culture are published [Man'ko, Chkhatarashvili 2020a, 2020b; Gabunia 1976; 2001; Gogitidze 2008; Varoutsikos et. al. 2017]. This complex, however, contains a series of tools

associated with hunting weapons, the analysis of which yields interesting information of great importance for the theory of archaeology.

We have previously published an article [Chkhatarashvili, Manko 2020] about the typological similarity between the Kobuletian Culture complexes and the M'lefaatian Culture (Middle East) and Kukrekian Culture complexes (Mountainous Crimea, Steppe zone of Ukraine and Moldova). Our observations were focused on the typology and absolute dates. It has been suggested that the migration of carriers of M'lefaatian Culture in Transcaucasia and Crimea was an event that extended over time. The theory arose that the migration of small groups of carriers of M'lefaatian Culture continued at least until the end of the 7th millennium BC.

Kvirike's materials may confirm our hypothesis. Some innovations in stone industry occurred simultaneously in the Middle East and Transcaucasia and the Crimea.

Materials and methods

The Kvirike site presents us with a limited range of sources for interpretation. The materials of the site are associated only with flint and obsidian artifacts. The acid soils of Western Transcaucasia prevent the preservation of organic matter, so faunal and microfaunal complexes are absent. Accordingly, only the analysis of the stone complex can enable us to analyze the cultural affiliation of the site.

We pay special attention to the typology of microliths because they were the most informative types of tools in the Stone Age. When we compare microliths of Kvirike with the complexes of neighboring territories, we took in account the idea that they appeared because of convergent development. That is why we are trying to find not only typological similarities but also similarities in the technology of microliths manufacturing. We also consider the correlation between the typology of microliths and the specific method of flint knapping. If we observe the complete similarity in the typology of microliths, similarity in the technology of their manufacture, a stable connection with a technique of blades obtaining, only in this case we draw conclusions about the connection between cultures that evolved at a remote distance. The map in fig. 1 shows us the most famous sites with conic and bullet-like cores and backed blade-

lets (M'lefaatian, Kobuletian, Kukrekian, and Donets Cultures).

We also observe changes in microlithic complexes during the development of different archaeological cultures. We regard the synchronous changes in typology and technology as further evidence of cultural links between the populations of South-Eastern Europe, Transcaucasia, and the Middle East in the Early Holocene.

Results. Kvirike: The Site of Kobuleti Culture. Site description

Kobuleti Culture is a phenomenon situated in Transcaucasia (West Georgia). The main sites are: Kobuleti, Khutsubani, Kvirike, Jikhanjuri, Anaseuli I [Gogitidze 1978], Darkveti (Layer V) [Nebieridze 1978], Sosruko (Layer M-1) [Bader 1965], Bavra, Bavra I and II [Gabunia 1976] (fig. 1). Radiocarbon dates indicate the time of development of Kobuleti Culture in frames of beginning of IX – beginning of VI millennium BC [Manko, Chkhatarashvili 2022].

Kvirike demonstrates the presence of all characteristics of Kobuleti Culture. Kvirike Site is located on the territory of the Kvirike Village in Adjara (Georgia), on a cape on the left bank of the Kinkishi River, 4 km from the seashore. The cape, surrounded by two riverbeds, occupies an area of about 50×50m, towering 15-20 m above the river level. The geographic position of site connected with the frontier of two landscape zones. Mountainous Kintrishi Gorge begins on right bank of Kinkishi and Kolkhis Ravine begins on the left bank. Inhabitants of site used resources of two landscape zones.

The Kvirike Site was discovered in 1970. S. Gogitidze investigated the site and made an 8×5 m trench [Gogitidze 1978]. Fragmentary publication of the material has taken place. We are republishing materials for this reason.

Items of flint (173) and obsidian (154) were found. Flint is of high quality, of pink color. Such flint is usually found in the valley of the Kintrishi River.

The locations of obsidian in Adjara are unknown. Nevertheless, the source of the obsidian has been ascertained. The inhabitants of the site brought it from Mount Chikiani (Javakheti), 200 km from Kvirike [Chkhatarashvili, Glascock 2022].

The strategies for using flint and obsidian were almost identical. As Table 1 shows, the typol-

Fig. 1. Map of Early Holocene sites with conic and pencil-like cores and backed bladelets and microblades. 1 – Ali Kosh; 2 – Chaga Sefid; 3 – Tepe Guran; 4 – Sabz; 5 – Sarab; 6 – Ganj Dareh; 7 – Asiab; 8 – Karim Shahir; 9 – Jarmo; 10 – M'lefaat; 11 – Hajji Firuz; 12 – Bavra, Bavra I, Bavra II, Bavra-Ablari; 13 – Kobuleti, Khutsubani, Kvirike; 14 – Anaseuli I; 15 – Darkveti (layer VI); 16 – Sosruko; 17 – Troitsa cape; 18 – Shan-Koba (layer IV); 19 – Kukrek; 20 – Ivanovka; 21 – Vishenne; 22 – Frontovoe I-IV; 23 – Mirnoe; 24 – Trapivka; 25 – Kam'yana Mogyla; 26 – Igren VIII; 27 – Kizleviy; 28 – Konetspol; 29 – Abuzova Balka; 30 – Varvarovka; 31 – Frumushika; 32 – Dobryanka I, II, III; 33 – Klisnya III, Zelena Gornitsa I, V, VI, Velika Pererva I.

ogy of flint and obsidian tools is roughly the same. But a major number of tools are made of obsidian. It is possible that there was a simple aesthetic preference. The tools made of obsidian do indeed look very beautiful. Obsidian is also easier to work with. We will describe the flint and obsidian complexes separately.

There are 173 flint artifacts.

Cores are absent, but we have 2 findings of tablets of round/oval form with D 1,2-1,5 cm. These tablets were removed from the upper parts of bullet-like cores (fig. 2,1-2).

There are 42 blades, bladelets, and microblades (Table 2), and their parts in the complex. Blades are not very wide. Their width is 1,2-1,4 cm. Bladelets have a width 0,7-1,2 cm, microblades – less when 0,7 cm. The whole pieces are no longer than 5 cm in length. There are 8 whole items, 13 proximal, 19 medial, and 2 distal parts. All blades, bladelets, and microblades were produced with the use of the hand-pressing technique. All products are straight or slightly curved along the pressing axis.

Primary flakes (D 4-5 cm) have a pebble cortex on dorsal surfaces. Secondary flakes have D 2-4 cm. There are 18 chunks and 5 chips too.

The total number of flint tools – 36. Half of them are burins (18). Findings of 4 burin spalls con-

nected with this type of tool. Only 1 dihedral angle burin was made on the primary flake (fig. 2, 7). Other burins were made on blades. There are 3 burins on truncated faceted blades (fig. 2, 8-9, 12), 8 angle burins on broken blades (fig. 2, 3-4, 11, 13, 15-17, 20), 2 angle bilateral burins (fig. 2, 6, 19), 1 double angle bilateral burin (fig.2, 10), 1 double angle burin with bipolar burins spalls (fig. 2, 18), 1 transverse burin (fig. 2, 14) and 1 dihedral symmetric burin (fig. 2, 5).

There are 4 scrapers. A round scraper was made on the medial part of the blade (fig. 2, 23), 2 oval scrapers (fig. 2, 22, 24), and 1 side scraper was made on flakes (fig. 2, 21).

There is 1 whole blade with stepped retouch on edge (fig. 2, 25), 4 medial parts of blades with fine retouched edges (fig. 2, 26-27, 30-31), and 1 medial part of the blade with flat retouch on edges on a ventral surface (fig. 2, 28). Only 1 notched blade of the complex was made on bladelet (fig. 2, 29).

Two perforators were found. Both tools were made on bladelets. The first perforator has arch-backed retouch on the edge (fig. 2, 32), the other item has an abrupt convergent retouch on the edges (fig. 2, 33). In complex we can see only 1 chisel on the flake (fig. 2, 34).

Types of artifacts	Total Number			Percentage		
	Flint	Obsidian	Total	Flint	Obsidian	Total
Cores and products of knapping						
Cores	0	2	2	0,00%	1,30%	0,61%
Tablets	2	0	2	1,16%	0,00%	0,61%
Blades	14	7	21	8,09%	4,55%	6,42%
Bladelets	22	9	31	12,72%	5,84%	9,48%
Microblades	6	10	16	3,47%	6,49%	4,89%
Primary flakes	7	2	9	4,05%	1,30%	2,75%
Secondary flakes	59	46	105	34,10%	29,87%	32,11%
Chunks	18	10	28	10,40%	6,49%	8,56%
Chips	5	0	5	2,89%	0,00%	1,53%
Burin spalls	4	2	6	2,31%	1,30%	1,83%
Tools	36	66	102	20,81%/100%	42,86%/100%	31,19%/100%
Burins	18	31	49	50,00%	46,97%	48,04%
Scrapers	4	2	6	11,11%	3,03%	5,88%
Retouched blades	6	5	11	16,67%	7,58%	10,78%
Notched blades	1	19	20	2,78%	28,79%	19,61%
Perforators	2	2	4	5,56%	3,03%	3,92%
Chisels	1	0	1	2,78%	0,00%	0,98%
Truncated blades	1	1	2	2,78%	1,52%	1,96%
Backed bladelets and microblades	3	6	9	8,33%	9,09%	8,82%
Total	173	154	327	100%	100%	100%

Table1. Kvirike. Flint and obsidian complexes.

There is a very interesting bitruncated blade in complex (fig. 2, 35). It's so-named "thin section", which was first described by F. Hole [Hole 1983, fig. 123]. We have another title for these artifacts type: "Kashkashok side-blow blade-flakes" [Nishiaki 1996, 311-325]. Such artifacts characterize the original method of segmentation of blades, which was common in the Early Middle Holocene in the Near and Middle East.

There are 3 microlithes in the complex: 1 backed (fig. 2, 37) and 2 partly backed medial parts of bladelets (fig. 2, 36, 38). Microliths of such type were used as inserts in bone points.

There are 154 obsidian artifacts.

Two cores were found. The first core is one-platform, has a conic form, has negatives from pressing of bladelets (fig. 3, 1). The second core has a bullet-like form, one-platform (fig. 3, 2).

Both cores have negatives of flakes rejuvenation on platforms.

There are 26 blades, bladelets, and microblades (Table 1), and their parts in the complex. Blades are not very wide. Their width is 1,3-1,6 cm. All pieces are not longer than 5 cm in length. There are 2 whole items, 8 proximal, 15 medial, and 1 distal part. All blades, bladelets, and microblades were produced with the use of the hand-pressing technique. All products are straight or slightly curved along the pressing axis.

There are 2 primary (d 3-4cm) and 46 secondary flakes (d 3-4 cm). There are 10 chunks (d less than 1 cm).

The complex contains 66 tools.

The most numerous types of tools are burins (31 items). We find two burin spalls from angle burins. All burins were made on blades. There are

such types: 18 angle burins on broken blades (fig. 3, 6, 12-19, 21, 23-27, 30-31, 33), 3 angle bilateral burins (fig. 3, 9, 22, 29), 1 double angle burin with bipolar burin spalls (fig. 3, 5, 10), 1 burin on truncated faceted blade (fig. 3, 20), 3 bilateral burins on truncated faceted blades (fig. 3, 3-4, 11), 1 transverse burin (fig. 3, 28), 1 dihedral angle burin (fig. 3, 8), There are 2 double burins with different proximal and distal parts: angle – bilateral angle

(fig. 3, 7) and transverse – bilateral on the truncated faceted blade (fig. 3, 32).

There are 2 scrapers: oval on the medial part of the massive blade (fig. 4, 1) and side scraper on the proximal part of the blade (fig. 4, 2).

Notched blades are represented as 3 proximal blades (fig. 4, 13-14, 16) and 16 medial parts of blades (fig. 4, 5-7, 9-12, 18-25). Among the retouched blades we see 2 items on whole blade (fig. 4, 15),

Fig. 2. Kvirike. Flint artifacts. 1-2 – tablets; 3-20 – burins; 21-24 – scrapers; 25-31 – retouched and notched blades; 32-33 – perforators; 34 – chisel; 35 – Kashkashok side-blow blade-flake; 36-38 – backed bladelets.

Fig. 3. Kvirike. Obsidian artifacts. 1-2 – cores; 3-33 – burins.

on proximal (fig. 4, 3-4) and 2 on medial (fig. 4, 20-21) parts of blades.

Perforators (2 items) have convergent abrupt retouches on the edges of badelets (fig. 4, 26-27).

The very rare tool is a truncated faceted blade with microburin spall (fig. 4, 28). This type of tool probably was used as arrow points.

There are 6 microliths in the complex. Among them we see 4 backed medial parts of microblades

(fig. 4, 29-32) and 2 proximal parts of blades with partly retouched edges (fig. 4, 33-34).

As we see, the typology of flint and obsidian tools is similar. But we must remark that carriers of Kobuleti Culture preferred obsidian for tool making.

The analysis of stone complex indicates a specific feature of site. The site function was the hunting camp (Table 1). More than 31 % of artifacts are tools. Only 114 flakes were found in complex. It's

Type	Quantity		
	Flint	Obsidian	All
Blades	2	2	4
Proximal parts	3	1	4
Medial parts	7	4	11
Distal parts	2		2
Bladelets	4		4
Proximal parts	10	4	14
Medial parts	8	5	13
Distal parts			0
Microblades	2		2
Proximal parts		3	3
Medial parts	4	6	10
Distal parts		1	1
Total	42	26	68

Table 2. Blades, bladelets, microblades.

a proof that the role of knapping was very low. In some time, we observe the process of tool making. We have proofs of making of burins on the territory of site (the presence of 6 burin spalls), proofs of making of hunting weapons (proximal part of backed bladelet). Such features relate with the short-term usage of site in process of hunting.

Discussion. The relative chronology of Kvirike Site and the question about late Kobuletian migration in East Europe

The Kvirike site hasn't absolute dates available, but we can observe the similarity of Kvirike with other Kobuletian complexes, most of which were dated earlier in frames of very beginning of Preboreal to beginning of Atlantic [Manko, Chkhatarashvili 2022]. All Kobuletian complexes demonstrate full similarity when we speak about non-microlithic tools. Only microlithic complexes demonstrate changes in time. Bavra and Bavra Ablari are the earliest Kobuleti Culture sites, which have Preboreal dates. Backed bladelets in Bavra complex are curved in profile and have bipolar retouch on sides sometimes. The non-geometric microlithic complex of Bavra correlated with geometrics, which demonstrates similarity with Zarzian geometric complexes. These are lunates, trapezes, triangles, which are fully absent in Kvirike.

The complex of Kobuleti (Layer 2) is older than Kvirike too. There are backed bladelets with

bipolar retouch in Kobuleti and curved in profile backed microblades. Bipolar backed bladelets are an indicator of coexistence with carriers of Trialetian, which disappeared in Boreal time. Kvirike complex contains straight backed bladelets and microblades. This fact may be the proof of youngest position of Kvirike.

The complex of Kobuleti (Layer 0) was investigated in 2021 and not published yet. We have a radiocarbon date of this complex in frames of very beginning of Atlantic (Table 3, 1). Flint and obsidian complexes demonstrate the full similarity with complex of Kvirike. The common features are presence of straight backed bladelets and microblades only.

The development of the microlithic complex is not the only evidence of the Atlantic age of Kvirike. We have a very rare "tool" in the complex: a so-called, Kashkashok side-blow blade-flakes (fig. 2, 35) [Nishiaki 1996, 311-325]. This type of tool is indicated in Georgia for the first time. The chronology of this type of tool is well known (Table 3, 2-14).

Kashkashok side-blow blade-flakes appeared in Late PPNB complexes: Abu Gosh [Khalaily et al. 2003, 25], Kfar Hahoresh [Vardi, Gilead 2011, 345], Gritile (Table 3, 2) [Stein 1992], Bouqras (Table 3, 8) [Bernbeck 1991]. This event took place at the second half of VIII – the beginning of VII millennia BC (cal.). This type of tool has not disappeared after the time of PPNB collapse. The usage of side-blow blade-flakes became an intercultural trend which connected with Proto-Hassuna (Kashkashok II, Bouqras; Table 3, 3-5, 9), Pre-Halaf (Sabi Abyad; Table 3, 6-7), and Late M'lefaatian (Hajji Firuz, Matarrah, Jarmo; Table 3, 10-14). As we can see from Table 1, all complexes are linked with side-blow blade-flakes developed in Early Atlantic times. This dating well corresponds with our relative chronology which was built on the backed bladelets analysis.

So, the appearance of Kashkashok side-blow blade-flakes connected with Early Atlantic. In this occasion, we propose a theory about appearance of this kind of tools in Eastern Europe in sometimes too. According to our theory, the appearance of these tools in Eastern Europe is presumably connected with a new migration of the Transcaucasian population. The appearance of the

Fig. 4. Kvirike. Obsidian artifacts. 1-2 – scrapers; 3-25 – retouched and notched blades; 26-27 – perforators; 28 – truncated blade with microburin spall; 29-34 – backed bladelets.

Donetsk Culture might have been the result of that migration.

Late Kukrek, in our opinion, cannot relate to migration from Transcaucasia. There are several Late Kukrekian complexes: Triytsa Cape (Table 3, 35-36) [Ianevich 2017], Kam'yana Mogila I [Danilenko 1984], Dobryanka I-III [Zalizniak et al. 2013]. All these complexes are linked with series of tools, which are fully absent in Kvirike: so-called, "Kukrek-type inserts". These are the medial parts of blades with retouched notches on corners and with negatives of flakes on the ventral surface. These

tools appeared at the beginning of Kukrekian Culture's development. So, Late Kukrekian developed the traditions of Early Kukrekian. The findings of Kukrek-type inserts are absent in Donetsk Culture complexes or present in very small numbers. The most famous Donetsk sites are Klishnya III (Table 3, 37-38) and IV, Zelena Gornitsa I, V, VI (Table 3, 39-41), Velika Pererva I (Table 3, 42), II [Man'ko 2006], Bondarikha II [Man'ko, Telizhenko 2020], Khutir Shevchenko [Gorelik 1987] (Tabl. 3). Donetsk sites are dated in frames of second half of VII – first half of VI millennia BC (cal) [Man'ko, Telizhenko 2003].

№	Date (BP uncal)	Lab. index	Sample	Site	Context	Publication
Kobuleti Culture						
1	7949±70	SPb-3623	charcoal	Kobuleti	Level 0	In first
Near and Middle East complexes with Kashkashok side-blow blade-flakes						
2	7770±150	Beta-8240	charcoal	Gritille	Faze B, PPNB	Stein, 1992
3	7880±110	TK-859	?	Kashkashok II	Level 3, Proto-Hassuna	Matsutani 1991
4	7730±90	TK-803	?	Kashkashok II	Level 3, Proto-Hassuna	Matsutani 1991
5	7490±110	TK-860	?	Kashkashok II	Level 3, Proto-Hassuna	Matsutani 1991
6	7720±50	GrN-24248	charcoal	Sabi Abyad*	Op. III, level 2, Pre-Halaf	Akkermans et al. 2006
7	6930±45	GrN-26924	charcoal	Sabi Abyad*	Op. II, level 2, Pre-Halaf	Akkermans et al. 2006
8	8155±45	GrN-8261	?	Bouqras	Level 4, Late PPNB	Bernbeck 1991
9	7465±45	GrN-10589	?	Bouqras	Level 3-4, Proto-Hassuna	Bernbeck 1991
10	7269±86	P-455	charcoal	Hajji Firuz	Layer D5, Late M'lefaatian	Chataigner 1995
11	6895±86	P-502	soil	Hajji Firuz	Layer 4, Late M'lefaatian	Chataigner 1995
12	6870±100	P-1843	charcoal	Hajji Firuz	Layer 6, Late M'lefaatian	Chataigner 1995
13	7570±50	W-623	charcoal	Matarrah	Op.IV-4 I, Hassuna	Bernbeck 1991
14	7655±75	GrN-6353	pottery	Jarmo	Layer 1, Late M'lefaatian	Braidwood et al. (eds.) 1983

Table 3. Absolute dates

We observe such similarities in Donetsk Cultures complexes and Kvirike.

1. The usage of pressing technique for obtaining blades, bladelets and microblades, presence of conic and pencil-like cores.

2. Backed bladelets and microblades are straight in profile.

3. Microburin technique we observe in big number of Donetsk sites (Khutir Shevchenko, Zelena Gornitsa I, V, VI, Bondarikha II).

4. The rare usage of flat ventral retouch.

5. Developed burins complexes, which contain similar types of burins (angle, on truncated faceted blades, bilateral, dihedral).

6. Similar types of scrapers, presence of retouched and notched blades, perforators.

7. The presence of Kashkashok side-blow blade-flakes in Klishnya IV and Bondarikha II complexes.

8. Technologic similarity in backed bladelets and microblades manufacturing. The presence of proximal parts of backed bladelets.

We must describe the thesis about technologic similarity in backed bladelets and microblades in details. We see in Kobuletian and Donetsk complexes all phases of microliths manufacturing.

Bullet-like cores were used for special fabrication of thin bladelets or microblades for their transformation in backed pieces. The first stage of their manufacturing was retouching of bladelet. Whole bladelets or microblades with refitting proximal part were used. We observe the appearance of

Chronology	M'lefaatian	Kobuletian	Kukrek and Donetsk Cultures
11200-9200 BP (uncal)	Karim Shahir, M'lefaat [Howe 1983; Dittermore 1983]	Bavra, Bavra I and II, Bavra Ablary [Gabunia 1976; Varoutsikos et al., 2017]	Abuzova Balka [Telegin 1985]
	The presence of conic and pencil-like cores, curved backed bladelets and backed bladelets with bipolar retouch, lunates of Zarzian origin.		
9200-7900 BP (uncal)	Ali Kosh (phase Ali Cosh) [Hole 1987]	Kobuleti [Man'ko, Chkhatarashvili 2020 a, b]	Mirnoye (Kukrek layer) [Stanko 1982]
	The disappearance of lunates.		
7900-7200 BP	Phase Surkh [Hole 1987]	Kvirike	Klishnya III [Man'ko 2006]
	The disappearance of curved backed bladelets and backed bladelets with bipolar retouch, dominance of straight backed bladelets. The appearance of Kashkashok side-blow blade-flakes		

Table 4. The development of Cultures with bullet-like cores and backed bladelets.

half-notches on proximal or near-proximal parts of bladelets. After what bladelets segmented, distal, and proximal parts of bladelets refitted with help of fingers pressing. Middle part of backed bladelet or microblade was ready to use after this procedure. The finger pressing gave a possibility to regulate longings of backed pieces, their straight profiles. Same partly backed pieces demonstrate us the aims of backing pieces. This aim was not to make retouched microliths. The main aim was making future insert with equal thickness of ends with rectangle form. The retouching of whole edge was not necessary. Backed pieces were inserts in bone points. Many numbers of such points were found in Ukrainian and Caucasian complexes [Kol'tsov 1989, 269, 288].

The difference of two Cultures is the presence of bifacial axes in Donetsk complexes. But it's not very important for us. Kobuletian Culture developed in conditions of pure raw materials base. In this occasion carriers of Kobuletian Culture used small chisels. Rich Donetsk raw material base changed this tradition.

Second difference is the presence of geometrics in Late Donetsk complexes. Such picture we observe in latest Kobuletian complexes (Anaseuli II) too [Nebieridze 1972]. So, its fact did not destroy our hypothesis about late Kobuletian migration.

Conclusion

Thus, the analysis of the Kvirike site and its comparison to the Kukrek and M'lefaat Cultures

complexes allowed us to clearly define its place among the industries characterized using bullet-like cores and backed bladelets. The results of this comparison are shown in Table 4.

As we see, the four different cultures developed quite synchronously, with changes in tool-making technology occurring in the same period in the Middle East, in Western Transcaucasia, and in southern Ukraine. This fact may indicate that the Donetsk, Kukrekian, Kobuletian, and M'lefaatian carriers created a continuous information space that continued to exist throughout the Early Holocene.

We can assume that the existence of this information space provided conditions for the spread of innovations of the Near and Middle East to the territory of Transcaucasia and Eastern Europe. We have traced the functioning of this information space on the example of the stone industry only. Nevertheless, it allows us to assume that this system could also provide the conditions for the spread of innovative Neolithic technologies.

The migration of Late Kobuletian population was the last of Kobuletian migrations on the territory of East Europe. The appearance of innovation technology of Kashkashok side-blow blade-flakes is a proof of existence of M'lefaatian-Kobuletian-Kukrekian-Donetsk unity in beginning of Atlantic.

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